

Mother Tongue Interference In Teaching English

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 10, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: June 11, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Teaching English, Language, Students</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8025208</p>	<p><i>A language is a means to see and understand the world. It is the means of expression of ideas, thoughts and perspectives of the world. Language therefore should be considered as part of culture and understanding in its context. Students learn English, because it is the superior number one language in the world. English is good for school students to understand subjects; the research investigates the effects of many factors on second language acquisition and the decline of English in secondary school. Vocabulary is systematically designed text that provides students with basic, yet comprehensive vocabulary in traction to improve both reading and writing competencies word meanings have many layers of meanings. Their messages can change depending on the time, the place and the situation in which they are used vocabulary is learning how to determine meaning. You will discover in working through his program, however, that learning vocabulary is not simply a memorization task. So vocabulary is important for teachers and students.</i></p>

Introduction

The Arabic mother tongue interference makes the students struggle to express themselves in English because of their teachers who teach them using Arabic words. Hence, the topic of learning English through using Arabic language is a topic of great struggling through a long period of time, so it is a controversial issue for most writers in the field of language acquisition. The researcher observed that secondary school students cannot understand English.

Objectives of the study

This research intends to

1. Figure out the ideal of teaching English language by using Arabic words for the secondary level students.
2. Understand the relation between teaching English and the different factors affecting the process of learning.
3. To discuss the impacts of teaching English language by using Arabic words.

Questions of the study

This research is an attempt to answer the following questions

1. What is the impact of using Arabic language in teaching English language?
2. Do most teachers use Arabic language in teaching English language?
3. Does Arabic language help the students to learn English well?

Hypothesis of the study

The hypothesis as follows

1. Mother tongue interference has a strong impact in teaching English.
2. Most EFL teachers fail in the mother tongue interference in teaching English language.
3. The mother tongue interference does not help the students to learn English well.

Significance of the study

Second language acquisition is obviously necessary for students to communicate with various communities and to know the different cultures. This study is very important for both policy makers and parents because it has a great effect on acquisition of a second language smoothly. And also for teachers and policy makers to be aware for their students, academic attainment because they are naturally not born fool.

Methodology of the study

Methodology of the study has adopted the descriptive analytical approach and the sample of the study has been selected from secondary schools students.

Literature review

2.0. Introduction

In this chapter the researcher points to the main topic through the literature review which is collected from different references.

2.1. Definitions of the language

To get enough and acceptable definition for the question above, we can say a definition is really condensed version of theory, and a theory is simply – or not so simply – an extended definition. Consider the following:

Ton (2006:120) defines that

language is a system of arbitrary, vocal symbols which permit all people in a given culture, or other people who have learned the system of that organs of speech and learning among members of a given community, and using vocal symbols possessing arbitrary conversational meaning.

* language is any set symbols of linguistic symbols as used in a more or less uniform fashion by a number of people who are thus enable to communicate intelligibly with one another (Random House Dictionary of the English language 1966:806)

* Language is a system of arbitrary vocal symbols used for human communication.

* (language) is any means, vocal or other of expressions or communicating feeling or thought... a system of conventionalized signs, especially words or gestures having fixed meanings (Webster's third new international dictionary of the English language 1934: 1390)

Still other common definitions found in introductory text books on linguistics include the concepts of:

1. The generative or creativity of language.
2. The presumed primacy of speech over writing.
3. The universality of language among human beings.

2.2. Language and Communication

2.2.1. Kinds of communication

All living creatures have some means of conveying information to others of their own group, communication being ultimately essential for their survival. Some use vocal noises, others physical movement or facial expression. Many employ a variety of methods. Birds use predominantly vocal noises as well as facial expression like the baring of teeth; insects use body movements, the most famous of which are the various "dances" of the bees. But man and human being has another best way of communication rather than whole animals.

Mavrides (2008: 383) says that

"Teaching English as a Foreign Language" talked about this vision and said " Man is able to exploit a range of techniques of communication. Many are in essence the same as those used by other creatures. Man is vocal, he uses his body for gesture of many kinds, he conveys information by facial expression, but he has extended these three basic techniques by adding the dimension of representation"

2.2.2. Learning and Teaching

What is learning and what is teaching and how do they interact?

A search in contemporary dictionaries reveals that **learning** is "acquiring or getting of knowledge of a subject or a skill by study, experience or instruction" a more specialized definition might read as follows:

Learning is relatively permanent change in behavioral tendency and is the result of reinforced practice"

Teaching may be defined as "Showing or helping some one to learn how to do something, giving instructions, guiding in the study of something, providing with knowledge, causing to know or understand"

Breaking down the components of the definition of learning, we can extract, as we did with language, domains of research and inquiry:

- 1- Learning is acquiring or "getting".
- 2- Learning is retention of information or skill.
- 3- Learning is retention implies storage systems, memory, cognitive organization.
4. Learning involves some active, conscious focus on and acting upon events outside or inside the organism.
5. Learning is relatively permanent of subject to forgetting.
6. Learning involves some forms of practice, perhaps reinforced practice.
7. Learning is a change in behaviour.

Teaching can not be defined apart from learning. Nathan Gage (1964: 264) noted that "to satisfy the practical demands of education, theories of learning must be stood on their head, so as to yield theories of teaching". Teaching is guiding and facilitating learning, enable the learner to learn, setting the conditions for learning.

If you view second language learning basically as a deductive rather than an inductive process, you will probably to present copious rules and paradigms to you students rather than let them "discover" those rules inductively. Jerome Bruner (1966: 40 – 41), noted that "a theory of instruction should specify the following features:

- 1- The experiences which most effectively implant in the individual a predisposition toward learning.
- 2- The ways in which a body of knowledge should be structured so that it can be most readily grasped by learner.
- 3- The most effectively sequences in which present the materials to be learned.
- 4- The nature and pacing rewards and punishments in the process of learning and teaching.

2.3. Teaching English as a foreign language

Teaching English as a foreign language (TEFL) refers to teaching English to students whose first language is not English. It usually occurs in the student's own country, either within the state school system, or privately, e.g. in an after-hours language school or with a one-on-one tutor. (TEFL) teachers may be native or non-native speakers of English.

Peter (2006: 117) claims that

To learn about the teaching of English on a wider scale, it is important to have an idea about the processes of English language learning and teaching, which have their own methodology and context, providing a full explanation of abbreviations (e.g. the difference between ESL and EFL, or TESOL as a subject and an organization).

2.4. Teaching techniques:

2.4.1. Reading

The technique of using literature aimed at children and teenagers for TEFL is rising in popularity. Both of these types of literature offer simpler material ("simplified readers" are produced by all the major publishers), and are often written in a more conversational style than literature aimed at adults. Children's literature in particular sometimes provides subtle cues to pronunciation, through rhyming and other wordplay. One technique for using these books is called the "multiple-pass technique". The instructor reads the book, pausing often to explain certain words and concepts. On the second pass, the instructor reads the book completely through without stopping.

2.4.2. Communicative language teaching

Ton (2006: 110) says that

Communicative language teaching (CLT) is an approach to the teaching of languages that emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of learning a language. Despite a number of criticisms,

[1] It continues to be popular, particularly in Japan, Taiwan, and Europe.

[2]. Task-based language learning (TBLL) is a particular approach to CLT which has been gaining ground in recent years. CLT is very important for developing and improving the students' skills in speaking, writing, listening and reading; otherwise the students would merely listen passively to the teacher without any interaction, which results in passive learning. It is the teacher's responsibility to encourage the students' creativity. These teachers have to enjoy what they are doing.

2.4.3. Blended learning

Blended learning is a combination of face-to-face teaching and online interactions (also known as CALL or Computer-Assisted Language Learning), which can be achieved through the adoption of a Virtual Learning Environment (VLE).

Mavrides, G. (2008:127) claims that

Virtual Learning Environment have been a major growth point in the ELT industry over the last five years. They are either developed as an externally-hosted platforms onto which content can be exported by a school or institution (a proprietary example is Web Course Tools, and an open source example is Model), or as content-supplied, course-managed learning platforms (e.g. the Macmillan English Campus). The key difference is that the latter is able to support course-building by the language school. This means that teachers can blend their existing courses with games, activities, listening exercises and grammar reference units that are contained online. This has applications in the classroom and as self-study or remote practice (for example in an internet café).

2.5. Some aspects of learning foreign language

There are some problem generally encounters the student during his study a foreign and his study a curriculum in a traditional way. To get a suitable way and some facilitates for learning a foreign language, we should understand that language is an acquiring knowledge and using language skills through speech not to gather more information and vocabulary without using it.

If we discuss briefly a distinction between acquisition and learning. The gradual development of ability in a language by using it naturally in communicative situation.

While the term "learning" however, applies to a conscious process of accumulating knowledge of the vocabulary and grammar of a language (mathematics, for example is learned not Acquired).

It can be assumed that the tasks and aims of foreign language teaching include the imparting to student of some or all the basic language skills – understanding speech, speaking, reading and writing, which he did not previously possess or which were present only in a limited form. One way of acquiring these skills is by experiencing them, by encountering them in use in real situation and coming to associate certain activities, persons or topic with the foreign language. This is what happens when the foreign is also the medium of instruction as English is in Nigeria and other countries.

Peter (2006: 119) claims that

In fact language is taught and learnt by different ways of devices, from this field, Peter Strevense (professor of applied linguistic) MAK Halliday (professor of General linguistic) and Angus McIntosh

language is taught and said " the language is taught, at least in part by the device of teaching in the language, by lessons in geography perhaps, or history or arithmetic. There is of course a danger here, the undoubted effectiveness of teaching in a foreign language as a means of teaching the language, does not mean that the language teacher supersedes the teacher of geography or history or mathematics"

The implementations of teaching can be clearly seen from the situation in countries such as Nigeria where we would see that English is the medium of instruction for almost all the teaching in secondary levels. This view has two significant consequences or results.

In the first place, the sheer quantity of classroom experience of English that pupil receives is much greater outside the English lesson than within it. But in the second place, the children are influenced by class teachers than those who specialized in English, so that the ultimate performance of teaching staff as whole rather than simply to the standard of specialized teacher of English.

To shadow more light on how a second language (L2) or native language (L1) is taught widely through the speech, we have several theories:

1- Every normal child quires the first language (native language) during the first year of his age, but there are exceptions, on either physical (e.g. deafness) or social ground (e.g. Wolf children).

2. Many young children whose parents speak different languages acquire a second language in circumstances similar to those of first language acquisition.

3. To let the child supply the language activity without to impose on him grammatical rules but we should encourage him how to speak only and how to imitate his mother or father by speaking the language.

The errors which often encounter the child in his study of the elementary school will be eliminated by the time, because such errors are self correcting. The child does not need to be taught that, for example the past of "catch" and also does not need to be taught the phonetic distinction between alveolar and velar plosives, children often mix these things together in the early stage of their ages, saying for example "tat" for "cat" but by gradually the child gets the correct way about how to use language and how to avoid the mistakes. For example you can see the child saying "between you and me" not "between you and I "or vice versa.

How is learning a second language different from learning your mother tongue?

The differences are due to three main factors: the age at which you learn, who teaches and how long you have to learn.

Generally, you learn a second language a lot late than you learn the first and this can give you certain advantages. Firstly, it means that you already have experience as a language learner and you are cognitively more mature. You also have a met linguistic knowledge; this means for example that you know what a word is and what it means to make a noun plural. Finally, you have a greater knowledge of people and the world.

This helps you to make good guesses at the meaning of unfamiliar language you encounter. On the other hand, the fact that you are older may mean that for fear of making mistakes or appearing silly.

The important teachers of your first language are of course your parents and immediate family, they generally have boundless patience and enthusiasm with your efforts to learn the language, and by intuition offer just the right kind of input is called to promote optimal language learning.

This modulated language input is called mothers, a feature of which is the fact that mistakes of fact are corrected where as mistakes of grammar generally are not. This all contrasts strongly with the teaching that many learners of a second language receive in the language classroom!

As far as available time is concerned, you are learning your mother tongue from the moment you were born (some say you start even before you born). You are then exposed to language every waking second of your day until the age of six or seven you have mastered its essentials.

That is an awful lot of time on task, and compares it with 3 or 4 hours a week in the typical foreign language classroom.

Flavell (2010:372) mentions that

In summary, every one learns their first language because they have the best teachers and the best circumstances, the most time and the least pressure and the greatest motivation. Learners of a second language have certain cognition advantages but none of the others, so it is not surprising how few go on to be as proficient in their second language as in their first.

2.6. Mother tongue interference

The term "mother tongue" should not be interpreted to mean that it is the language of one's mother. In some paternal societies, the wife moves in with the husband and thus may have a different first language, or dialect, than the local language of the husband. Yet their children usually only speak their local language. Only a few will learn to speak their mothers' languages like natives. Mother in this context probably originated from the definition of mother as source, or origin; as in mother-country or –land.

In some countries such as Kenya and India, "mother tongue" is used to indicate the language of one's ethnic group (ethnic tongue), in both common and journalistic parlance (e.g. 'I have no apologies for not learning my mother tongue', rather than one's first language.

Tarone (1989: 152) mentions that;

A similar usage of the term was employed in Ireland in the early-to-mid twentieth century, with Irish being referred to as the "mother tongue" of all Irish people, even of those whose first language was English.

Also in Singapore, "mother tongue" refers to the language of one's ethnic group regardless of actual proficiency, while the "first language" refers to the English language, which is the lingua franca for most post-independence Singaporeans due to its use as the language of instruction in government schools and as a working language despite it not being a native tongue for most Singaporeans. The same applied for [Malaysia.]

International Mother Language Day Monument in Sydney, Australia, unveiling ceremony, 19 February 2006

J. R. R. Tolkien in his 1955 lecture English and Welsh distinguishes the "native tongue" from the "cradle tongue", the latter being the language one happens to learn during early childhood, while one's true "native tongue" may be different, possibly determined by an inherited linguistic taste, and may later in life be discovered by a strong emotional affinity to a specific dialect (Tolkien personally confessed to such an affinity to the Middle English of the West Midlands in particular).

2.7. The significance of one's mother tongue

It is very important for one to learn how to communicate with their surroundings as it is impossible to live without communication. If a person is mute or deaf, they must learn how to speak by using sign language. One characteristic of language as the mother tongue is finding names for objects and persons within the child's reach, so it is possible for a child to grasp, repeat and understand the world.

Wahba (1998: 170) says that;

One's mother tongue makes it possible for a child to take part in the knowledge of the social work. Another impact of the mother tongue is that it brings about the reflection and learning of successful social patterns of acting and speaking. It is basically responsible for differentiating the linguistic competence of acting.

But there are also many people who prefer to speak and communicate in their second language rather than their mother tongue. They feel more comfortable in the second language because their mother tongue might be very limited and does not provide a great amount of words or expressions.

Language is a medium of communication within the family and society. Every tongue expresses the culture of society to the complete satisfaction of its members. The language an individual speaks is for him or her most expressive and often the most beautiful of all languages.

If language is denied to anyone, the following experiment will show what happens; Friedrich the second of Hohenstaufen (1194-1250) conducted the following experiment: He ordered some orphans to be brought to the palace where they should be observed while being brought up. He arranged every kind of physical care for the babies banned any kind of verbal or emotional physical contact. Thus he tried to find out which language the infants would speak naturally.

It was expected that it would be Hebrew, Greek or Latin, formerly regarded as the original languages. But it was neither one of these languages nor the language of the children's parents - the children did not speak any language at all: they died.

Willems (1987: 351)

This experiment shows and has been proved by several psychological studies that language is not only a product of human life it is the prerequisite of it. Or in other words, human beings require a human relationship to survive. These children were neither exposed to non-verbal expressions of emotions such as gestures, nor to speech.

On multilinguality

One can have two or more native languages, thus being a native bilingual or indeed multilingual. The order in which these languages are learned is not necessarily the order of proficiency. For instance, a French-speaking couple might have a daughter who learned French first, then English; but if she were to grow up in an English speaking country, she would likely be proficient in English.

The Brazilian linguist Cleo Altenhofen considers the denomination "mother tongue" in its general usage to be imprecise and subject to various interpretations that are biased linguistically, especially with respect to bilingual children from ethnic minority groups. He cites his own experience as a bilingual speaker of Portuguese language and Riograndenser Hunsrückisch, a German-rooted language brought to southern Brazil by the first German immigrants. In his case, like that of many children whose home language differs from the language of the environment (the 'official' language), it is debatable which language is his 'mother tongue'. Many scholars gave definitions of 'mother tongue' through the years based on common usage, the emotional relation of the speaker towards the language, and even its dominance in relation to the environment. However, all of these criteria lack precision.

2.8. Teacher cognition and decision - making

In the field of language teaching and learning, research in classroom pedagogy has adopted the process-product view which regards teaching as a linear process relating teachers' behaviour to outcomes in students' learning (Cochran-Smith and Lytle 1990). However, classroom-centred research has now acknowledged that any research account of understanding teaching should involve an inner exploration of teacher cognition-how teachers conceive of what they do, taking into account their knowledge, reasoning, beliefs and assumptions about teaching and learning (Burns 1992 and Freeman 1996).

Woods (1996) and others researching on teacher cognition believe that teachers bring with them a store of knowledge, experience and beliefs which invariably influence their decision making in the classroom. This cognition is a product of the teachers' past learning and teaching experiences which they bring with them to the class and which could be acquired both from training or experience.

Tarone (1977: 325) describes this 'cognitive system' as

"a product of an individual teacher's past learning and teaching experiences, beliefs about teaching and learning from both professional training as well as her own folk wisdom gleaned from fellow teachers and her particular personality"

2.9. A Description of Arabic

Phonology

The Arabic and English phonological systems vary extensively, not only in the range of sounds used, but also in the relative importance of vowels and consonants in expressing meaning. While English has 22 vowels and diphthongs to 24 consonants, Arabic has only eight vowels and diphthongs to 32 consonants.

Consonant Clusters

English has far more consonant clusters than Arabic. Some initial two-segment clusters which Arabic does not have corresponding equivalents to, include: pr, pl, gr, thr, thw, sp. The three-segment initial consonant clusters are entirely absent in Arabic, e.g., clusters such as spr, skr, str, spl. Faced with the challenge of such consonant clusters, Arabic speakers will often insert short vowels in order to "assist" pronunciation in the following manner:

'perice' or 'pirice' for price

'ispring' or 'sipring' for spring

The range of consonant clusters appearing at the end of words is also much smaller in Arabic. In dramatic contrast to English, which has 78 three-segment clusters and fourteen four-segment clusters occurring at the end of words, Arabic has none. Again, faced with such terminal clusters, Arabic speakers tend to insert short vowels to assist pronunciation:

'arrangid' for arranged

'monthiz' for months

'nexist' for next

Teachers will often encounter examples of such pronunciations, which also can carry over into the spelling of such English words by students whose mother tongue is Arabic.

2.10. Influence of English Spelling on Pronunciation

While there are no similarities between the Arabic and English writing systems, Arabic spelling within its own system is simple and virtually phonetic. Letters stand directly for their sounds. Arabic speakers attempt, therefore, to pronounce English words using the same phonetic methodology. Add to this the salience of consonants in Arabic and you get severe pronunciation problems caused by the influence of the written form:

'istobbid' for stopped (the 'p' sound does not exist in Arabic)

'forigen' for foreign

2.10.1. Grammar.

The grammatical structure of Arabic, a Semitic language, is very different from that of Indo-European languages such as English. These great differences must be borne in mind when Arabic speakers are mixed with European students.

The basis of the Arabic language is the three-consonant root. A notion such as writing, cooking, or eating is represented by three consonants in a particular order.

Kambal (1980: 71) claims that

All verb forms, nouns, adjectives, participles, etc. are then formed by putting these three-root consonants into fixed vowel patterns, modified sometimes by simple prefixes and suffixes.

Example.1.

Root /k/ /t/ /b/ (= writing)

A person who does this for a living kattaab (= a writer)

Passive participle maktoob (= written)

Present tense yaktubu (= he writes it)

Example.2.

Root /g/ /r/ /h/ (= wounding or cutting)

A person who does this for a living garraah (= a surgeon)

Passive participle magrooh (= wounded or a battle casualty)

Present tense yagruhu (= he wounds him)

There are over 50 such patterns. While not all forms are found for each root, the three-consonant root is the structural basis of the language.

It follows that Arabic speakers have great difficulty in grasping the confusing range of patterns for all words in English; that nouns, verbs, and adjectives follow no regular patterns to distinguish one from another, and may, indeed, have the same orthographic form. Such regularities of morphology as English has, particularly, in the area of affixes, will be readily grasped by Arabic speakers, e.g. -ing, -able, un-, etc.

2.10.2. Word Order.

In formal written Arabic the verb comes first followed by the subject. This convention is followed more in writing than in speech, and may transpose to English writing:

e.g. Decided the minister yesterday to visit the school.

2.10.3. Questions and Negatives; Auxiliaries.

The auxiliary "do" has no equivalent in Arabic. Where no specific question word is used, a question is marked only by its rising intonation:

e.g. You went to London?

You like coffee?

Note that the Arabic for "where?" is "wayn?", which is often confused with "when."

Negatives are formed by putting a particle (laa or maa) before the verb:

e.g. He not play football.

The Verb to Be

There is no verb "to be" in Arabic in the present tense. The copula (am, is, are) is not expressed. It is therefore, commonly omitted in English by Arabic speakers, particularly in present progressive forms:

e.g. He teacher.

The boy tall.

He going to school .

2.10.4. Articles.

There is no indefinite article in Arabic, and the definite article has a range of use different from English. The indefinite article causes particular problems as it is commonly omitted with singular and plural countable:

e.g. This is book or This book (for This is a book)

He was soldier

When the English indefinite article has been learned by the Arabic speaker, it tends to be used wherever the definite article is not used:

e.g. There are a books.

I want a rice.

Kambal (1980: 71) claims that

There is a definite article form in Arabic, though it takes the form of a prefix (al-). It is used, as in English, to refer back to indefinite nouns previously mentioned, and also for unique reference (the sun, on the floor, etc)

The most common problem with the definite article arises from interference from the Arabic genitive construction

English

Arabic

John's book. (or The book of John.) Book John.

A man's work. (or The work of a man.) Work man.

The teacher's car. (or The car of the teacher.) Car the teacher.

Most errors of word order and use of articles in genitive constructions are interference of this kind:

e.g. This is the book the teacher.

This is the key door.

It follows that Arabic speakers have great difficulties with the Saxon genitive construction.

The special cases in which English omits the article, e.g. in bed, at dawn, on Thursday, for breakfast, etc. usually take the definite article in Arabic:

e.g. At the sunset we broke our fast.

What would you like for the breakfast?

All days of the week, some months in the Muslim calendar, and many names of towns, cities and countries include the definite article in Arabic, which is often translated, appropriately or not:

e.g. We lived in the India.

We had a flat in the Khartoum.

On Monday we went to Cardiff.

2.10.5. Adjectives and Adverbs.

Adjectives follow nouns in Arabic and agree in gender and number. This may cause beginners to make mistakes:

e.g. He is man tall. (for He is a tall man).

Adverbs are used less commonly in Arabic than in English and, except for adverbs of time, do not have a fixed pattern. Adverbs of manner are often expressed in a phrase: quickly is expressed "with speed", and dangerously as "in a dangerous way." There is frequent confusion between the adjective and adverb forms in English, and the adjective form is usually overused:

e.g. He drives very dangerous .

2.10.6. Prepositions and Particles.

Arabic has a wealth of fixed prepositions and particles, with both verbs and adjectives. Many of these do not coincide with their direct English translations:

e.g. to arrive to

to be short of

afraid from

angry on

near from

an expert by

2.10.7. Some prepositions have verbal force:

"·On" expresses obligation:

e.g. It is on me that I pay him.

"·To" and "for" express possession:

e.g. This book is to me / for me. (for This book is mine).

"·With" expresses present possession:

e.g. With me my camera. (for I have my camera with me).

"·For" expresses purpose:

e.g. I went home for (I) get my book. (for I went home to get my book).

2.10.7. The Active and Passive Voices.

There are active and passive forms for all tenses in Arabic, but they are virtually identical, differing only in the (unwritten) short vowelling. A passive verb in a text is therefore only recognizable as such from its context. The passive voice is used far less frequently in Arabic writing than in English, and hardly at all in everyday speech. Thus while the concepts of active and passive will readily be understood, the uses and forms of the passive cause problems.

2.10.8. Vocabulary.

The acquisition of vocabulary is particularly difficult for Arab learners of English. Only a minimal number of words in English are borrowed from Arabic. A small range of mainly technical words, such as computer, radar, helicopter, and television, have been taken into Arabic, but these are common to most languages. Arabic speakers have very few aids to reading and listening comprehension by virtue of their first language, and they should not be expected to acquire English at anything like the same pace as European learners.

2.10.9. Punctuation.

Arabic punctuation is now similar to western style punctuation, though some of the symbols are inverted or reversed, e.g. a reversed question mark and comma. The use of full stops and commas is much freer than in English, and it is common to begin each new sentence with And or So. Connected writing in English tends therefore to contain long, loose sentences, linked by commas and "ands

Freeman (1990) holds the view that the teacher has a 'mental life' which influences and directs what happens in the class. Like Ulichny (1996) he suggests that teachers' mental lives' do not begin when they enter teacher education programmes but rather they bring to this formal training, a background of tacit knowledge and personal theories about classrooms and what goes on in them. This view argues that knowledge resides within the teacher and is more personal, experiential and individual in nature. It suggests that teachers hold personal views of themselves, their learners, their goals, and their roles which influence the kind of leaning environment they try to create in their classrooms. This cognitive system is also believed to be manifested in the form of 'rational principles' or 'maxims.

Willems (1987) says that

Premised on this view that teaching has a cognitive component and that teachers possess cognitive systems which influence their decision making, it is necessary to explore how teachers' cognitive systems inform their decision making in relation to their LI use. In exploring teachers' cognition, this study also attempts to understand teaching from the perspective of the teachers themselves, to pay attention their often 'hidden voices' in order to understand the complexity of life in language classrooms.

2.11. Critical problems in English language teaching and learning

What can the teacher do?

English language students, you can't live with them, you can't do without them. What's a frustrated English as a Foreign or Second language teacher going to do? English language teachers, there are good ones, so-so ones and then there are those that justice would only prevail if they were permanently excused from the classroom. So what's a near-desperate English as a foreign language learner to do?

2.11.1. Critical Problems .

Here are the first three of the English language learning classroom's most critical problems with comments on what might be done in dealing or managing each one.

2.11.2. Lack of Learner Motivation.

Students skip class, and when they do show up it's likely due to fear of failure more than anything else. They may lack any semblance of attention during class, chatting with classmates, doodling in their note books or, (gasp!) in their textbooks. What experienced English or other foreign language teaching professional hasn't faced the problem of reluctant, unmotivated learners? One key to increasing motivation is to use activities matched to the personalities, learning styles and characteristics of the learners as often as practically possible.

The problem of not motivated students, the lack of time for the processes of learning, and the excess of students in each classroom is structural in this society with the proper responsibility of the current government and the Governments that have preceded the current, and does not just affect the teaching of English language, but affects almost all school subjects to be taught in both basic primary and secondary education and can be lower than in proportion to the university training. The point is that we must be part of the solution and not part of the problem.

Lack of motivation, poor resources and over-crowded classes are undoubtedly some of the most critical problems that teachers have to face in our schools, not only to teach English, but also almost all the subjects.

Lack of motivation may be the result of many factors as the way itself that subject are presented to them; most of the time students find the contents have nothing to do with the actual world. Many students, I believe, feel that stay in school six hours a day, is a completely waste of time because subjects don't meet their wants or needs; on the other hand most of the students don't have goals to achieve, they don't know where they want to go then are teachers who must always be looking for methods and strategies to motivate and make learning challenger to get better results and one of them is to take in account the multiple intelligences to prepare activities.

George (1978: 84) mentions that

About lack of resources, insufficient time and over-crowded groups, the responsibility is of our educational system but teachers have to use their creativity to overcome the problem. I've found so useful using practices of Dynet method as circuit training, choral and groups activities to work with either small or large courses and to get recourses I've used many strategies from taking the students toys until make the students prepare cards and posters that have been used before with other courses.

There are many problems but there are many teachers trying to solve them.

2.11.3. Insufficient Time, Resources and Materials.

It is known that in old edes, "A man can never be too rich, too thin or have enough English or foreign language vocabulary. So what can the teacher do when charged with teaching English or a foreign language in only one or two hours per week? One of the only times that was ever successfully accomplished was with the pouring out of Holy Spirit on the apostles during Pentecost. (Acts 2:1 – 11) Add too little time to a decided lack of resources and virtually zero other resources in many third-world classrooms and you have a critical teaching / learning situation indeed. But there are ways, even on the lowest budget, of producing virtually free or very inexpensive English language teaching and learning aids for use in the EFL or foreign language classroom.

2.11.4. Over-Crowded English Classes;

George (1978: 84) mentions that

The number of learners in a class room can range from one, for those who teach individual private learners, to 15 or twenty learners in a typical classroom up to "multitudes of 35 or forty or even fifty or more learners packed into a language leaning situation. Forget anything even remotely resembling "individual attention". Either the throng "gets it" or they don't with little available to the teacher.

When the teacher is faced with over-sized groups he immediately implements strategies using choral, small group and pair work to help in lessening the load on both him and my large group of learners. He also separates out a few of the more "advanced" learners to help me with group work elements. It doesn't solve all the problems, but it's a good start.

While it would be absolutely impossible to provide detailed answers to such critical, world-wide problems in the English language teaching and learning classroom here, we can recognize our limitations and constraints, and collectively make an effort to address and overcome them. If you have ideas on any of these problem topics, feel free to share them in comments, e-mails, forums, ELT conferences and teacher meetings. Who knows, your voice may be just the one to break open the problem with a universally workable approach or solution.

George (1978: 87) mentions that

One of the common problems at teaching English, in this case, is the over-crowded class where a teacher can find more than thirty students in a very small classroom, without a tape recorder, no television, no posters, no DVD or sometimes without markers neither board. It is always difficult to carry out activities where students can improve their communicative skills; is not possible to personalize teaching and as consequence not good results are shown every day.

Besides this, the class-time is often very short (once or twice a week, one or two hours daily), so the lesson plan is not developed as programmed was and next class is often a review of the last one stopping the teaching-learning process. The teacher does not know what problems there are in the students learning process, he or she cannot to solve them because is difficult to distinguish a specific learner with a specific learning problem.

2.12. English as a second Language Teaching Strategies.

Coady (1988). States that:

" Does preparation make any difference? All teachers know that well prepared lessons can go badly, and unprepared lessons can sometimes go well. However, in the vast majority of cases your classes will be significantly improved by preparing well.

How should a teacher prepare? ESL teaching strategies for preparing include: deciding exactly what you want to do in the class, and how you will achieve your aims is the most important. Other things include: collecting together all the things you need before going into the classroom; thinking of original ways of practicing the language; writing short readings/listenings for the students; making photocopies; preparing questions or exercises; checking that the CD player works and is plugged in; checking that your markers are full of ink; checking that the classroom you are using has an eraser and that the chairs are in order for your class; reading through any materials you will be using in class; deciding which words need explanation and practice, and how you will explain and practice; planning a few short filler activities in case you finish early.

As well as the above preparation for an individual class, sometimes it's important to think about the long term planning of a class. This would involve thinking about the needs and aims of the students, do they need help with exams for example.

There are different ways of presenting new vocabulary;

Stage. 1.

Ideas for presenting specific select an item from the vocabulary taught in a foreign language. Texts book how the meaning of this item would best be presented to learners who are encountering it for the first time and note down some ideas if you are working in groups then get together share ideas and contribute new ones to each other.

Stage .2.

Application and comparison

Identify which ones are more of the techniques were used in your own ideas for presentation

Ideas for vocabulary work in the classroom

Sharing ideas:

Stage. 1. Preparation

Each participant prepares a vocabulary activity which they think is effective. Teachers with some experience or find suggestions in books or simply create new own.

Stage. 2, Presentation

The activities are presented to the group this is best done by actually performing them the presenter role playing and the other students in this way you get feed of the procedure and remember it well.

But doing this way is rarely time consuming, so in large group some people may have to simply describe their activities or present them in written form.

2.13. Using Realia in teaching vocabulary;

'Realia' in EFL terms refers to any real objects we use in the classroom to bring the class to life. In this tip I'd like to offer a few suggestions for activities using realia and to consider why we may want to bring things into the class.

Why use realia in class?

Rivers, W. M. (1981)), says that

"The main advantage of using real objects into the classroom is to make the learning experience more memorable for the learner. To give a couple of simple examples, if you are going to teach vocabulary of fruit and vegetables it can be much more affective for students if they can touch, smell and see the objects at the same time as hearing the new word. This would appeal to a wider range of learner styles than a simple flashcard picture of the piece of fruit or vegetable. (With very young learners, classroom management can become trickier if you bring in real objects as excitement levels tend to rise. Last year one of my students bit into an onion we were passing round. I'm sure he hasn't forgotten that class!)

A second example would be if you are going to teach some functional language for asking for the timetable for a train. You could use a fictitious timetable or you could use a real one from the local train station, one from the internet, or if you're really organized, some you brought back from your last trip to the UK. This way you expose students to more language than simply the times and destinations. They will see information about prices, discounts, bank holidays etc.

Here is a selection of activities involving realia.

Tourist information

Rivers, W. M. (1981), says that

"Gather some city/town maps from the tourist information bureau wherever you are. Use them to create role plays that could happen with English speaking visitors to their town or city. Give students a scenario for them to build a role play out of. If you had trouble finding your way around their town/ city when you arrived use your own experiences to create situations.

Collect brochures of places of interest (in English if possible but not vital) and ask students to use them to plan a trip for a group of students who are coming to their town for a week. They can plan the itinerary, work out the budget etc,

Concentration

See the games archive for instructions on how to play this game. <http://teachingenglish.org.uk/language-assistant/games/concentration>

Instead of using students' names put an object, such as an item of clothing or a classroom object, in front of each student and that is what they say instead of their names to pass the turn around the circle.

Recycling race

O'Harra, K.E.(1984), mentions that

(Depending on the recycling facilities in your country you will need to adapt the task accordingly) For this you just need a bag of rubbish (clean items out first) that you are about to recycle like tetrabriks, glass jars, cereal boxes, tins, old newspapers etc.

To introduce the idea of recycling ask students what all the objects are and which container they'd put them in to recycle them. Draw a picture of each of the possible containers and get students to come and choose an item and tell the class where they'd put it to recycle it and why. You could make this into a team race by giving each team the mission of collecting all the items for their container one by one. You could then use the recyclable material to make a poster with your students about recycling.

For older students elicit the vocabulary for the items and materials and lead on to a discussion or class survey about recycling.

Island survival

Bring in a selection of items such as a coat hanger, a corkscrew, a packet of dental floss, a clothes peg, a plastic bag, a wooden spoon, some swimming goggles, elastic bands etc. Put the students into groups and tell them they have been ship wrecked on a desert island with their group. Luckily there are some random items on the island they can use to help them survive. Reveal the items one by one and elicit vocabulary. Then tell students they have ten minutes to think about how they are going to use the items to help them survive. At the end, listen to each group's ideas and vote on which group you think would survive the longest.

Identity envelopes

(Thanks to Lucy Mardel for this activity.) Get three or four envelopes and fill them with bits and bobs you find around the house such as foreign currency, shop receipts, postcards, photos, buttons, etc. Put students into groups and ask them to have a good look at the objects and to decide who they belong to. They should be able to build up the identity of a character from the objects. You could say they are all suspects from a crime and they have to decide who did it, or simply create the characters to use in a role play.

CONCLUSION, FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The study investigates the area of teaching English through by the effects of the Arabic language interference.

The purpose of the study is to identify the problems of the mother language interference that face the EFL teachers in teaching English language. Besides the study aims at attempting to find suitable solutions to the problems that resulted in using Arabic language in teaching English at secondary level.

Findings

From the analysis of data the researcher has reached to the following finding:

- a. Most of the EFL students commit errors in using English language according to the mother language interference in the language used by their teachers.
- b. There is a problematic area in pronouncing specific letters for the students caused by using Arabic in teaching English

- c. The time of the lesson is not quite enough to enable the students to practise speaking in order to solve the problems caused by the mother language interference.
- d. Most of EFL teachers are not qualified in teaching English language.

Recommendations

Under the lights of the findings the researcher would like to recommend the following:

- a. EFL teachers should be well trained in teaching English language.
- b. EFL teachers should be well qualified in developing their students in English language.
- c. EFL teachers should give their students additional activities in speaking.
- d. EFL teachers should divide the students into groups in order to develop their learning abilities.
- e. EFL teachers should correct their students' mistakes in using English language.
- f. There should be extra time for speaking in English..

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